

STUDYING THE EFFECTIVENESS AND SAFETY OF THE INFLUENCE OF MEDIUM DOSES OF UVA-1 RADIATION ON THE CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF PSORIASIS

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Psoriasis is a chronic immune-mediated inflammatory disease that occurs in 2-4% of people worldwide, affecting the skin and 30% of the joints (psoriatic arthritis) [1]. It is characterized by recurrent skin plaques, hyperproliferation of epidermal keratinocytes, and thickening of the skin [2, 3]. Psoriasis is also marked by an increased abundance of immune cells and inflammatory biomarkers at both local and systemic levels.

Along with the symptoms of psoriasis, there is an increased tendency to cardiovascular diseases, autoimmune diseases, including diabetes, which further reduces the quality of life and increases the severity of the disease. [4]. Psoriasis occurs in both genders predominantly under the age of 60 years (the peak falls on the period from 16 to 22 years) in 70% of cases [5].

In the development of the psoriatic process, the key role is played by the system of regulatory polypeptides - cytokines, the imbalance of which causes immunopathological changes in the body of patients [Dolgikh V.T., 1998; Evstafiev V.V., 2000; Christophers E., 1996; Allen M., et al., 2001]. In particular, psoriasis is characterized by the predominance of pro-inflammatory cytokines, which are produced by Th1-lymphocytes (γ -IFN), macrophages, Langerhans cells (IL-1 β), Th17-lymphocytes (IL-17) [Astrid].VanBeelenetal.,2007;ChristophersE.,1996]. In turn, modern methods of treating psoriasis, including phototherapy, have a normalizing effect on the balance of cytokines, which allows us to regard the cytokine profile indicators as a kind of marker of the severity of the course and, possibly, the effectiveness of the treatment of this dermatosis [DaweR.S. et al., 2003; GambichlerT. et al., 2007; GooperK.D.etal., 1990;H. VanLoverenetal., 2004].]. However, despite the study of the most important pathogenetic aspects of dermatosis, its treatment remains one of the urgent problems of modern dermatology [KutasevichYa.F. et al., 2002; Sukharev A. V., 2009]. The choice of treatment option for patients with psoriasis should be strictly individualized, taking into account the prevalence

and severity of the psoriatic process, somatic status and possible response to the proposed treatment, experience of previous therapy, assessment of the quality of life, motivation and compliance of the patient to treatment [Khobeish M.M., 2009]. Phototherapy is considered as one of the key directions in the treatment of dermatological patients. In recent years, in the treatment of a number of dermatoses, narrow-spectrum UV radiation has been widely used, which has a selective effect on the structures of the skin with less pronounced side effects (for example, narrow-spectrum UVB radiation at 311 nm), which has a distinct anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive effect [Kostovic K., Pasic A., 2004; Morita A., Kobayashi K., Isomura I, et al., 2000]. Compared to the general range of UVA (320-400 nm) and UVB, UVA-1 (340-400 nm) radiation penetrates the skin more deeply [Cordoro K.M, 2008]. This type of radiation has been successfully used in connective tissue diseases and severe forms of atopic dermatitis [Tzaneva S. et al., 2001], and without the use of photosensitizers. This spectrum of radiation in therapeutic doses does not cause erythema on the skin and can be used in pediatric practice [Morita A. et al., 2000; Tzaneva S. et al., 2001]. The efficacy and safety of long-range long-wave UVA-1 therapy in the treatment of a number of dermatoses, including atopic dermatitis and scleroderma, can be considered proven [Kubanov A.A., 2010; Tzaneva S. et al., 2001].

The aim of the study: To study the effect of medium doses of UVA-1 (wavelength 370nm) radiation on the clinical manifestations of progressive psoriasis and the cytokine profile of patients suffering from this dermatosis.

Materials and research methods. We examined 70 patients with psoriasis aged 18 to 60 years, 45 (64.3%) men and 25 (35.7%) women. The control group consisted of 30 patients receiving PUVA therapy. The criteria for inclusion of patients in the observation group were: the presence of clinically confirmed moderate to severe psoriasis. Criteria for exclusion from the study: the presence of psoriatic arthritis of any severity; an indication in the anamnesis of a cytostatic, immunosuppressive therapy carried out no later than 6 months; a history of biological therapy; the presence of severe concomitant somatic pathology and infectious diseases in the stage of decompensation; the use of systemic corticosteroids within 6 months prior to the start of this study. The course of the psoriatic process was assessed using dermatological indices of coverage and severity of psoriasis PASI (Psoriasis Area and Severity Index), as well as quality of life - DLQI (Dermatology Life Quality Index) [Finlay Y., Khan Gk., 1992; Krueger G.G. et al., 2000; Jacobson C.C., Kimball A.B., 2004]. In 20 (28.57%) patients, the PASI index was in the range of up to 10, in 33 (47.14%)

patients, the PASI index fluctuated in the range of 10-35. Index values over 35 were recorded in 17 (24.29%) patients. 45 (64.3%) patients described dermatosis as a disease that significantly worsens the quality of life (DLQI 21-30), 18 (25.7%) patients noted a moderate effect of psoriasis on the quality of life (DLQI 11-20), 7 (10 %) of patients, respectively weak (DLQI 1-10). In 33 (47%) cases, the psoriatic process was limited, in 37 cases (53%) it was widespread. The vulgar variety of dermatosis was registered in 45 (64%) patients; exudative - in 9 (13%), seborrheic - in 16 (23%). The main group consisted of 40 patients who received long-range long-wave UVA-1 therapy using a Waldmann UV1000 KL photocabin (Herbert Waldmann Gmb H&Co, Germany) (registration certificate no. -400 nm) and emission maximum $n\lambda=370$ nm. Phototherapy sessions were performed 5 times a week. Starting from a dose of 50 J/cm^2 , the dose was successively increased by 5 J/cm^2 until the maximum single exposure dose of 70 J/cm^2 was reached.

As a comparison group, 30 patients were observed who received general PUVA therapy using a universal ultraviolet cabin Waldmann UV 7002K (Germany, 2010). The procedures were carried out according to the method of 5 times exposure per week with a gradual increase in the UVA dose by 0.5 J/cm^2 . Two hours before the session, patients orally took the photosensitizer oxoralen (manufactured by Gerot Pharmazeutika, GmbH, Austria). The initial dose of ultraviolet radiation was $0.5-1 \text{ J/cm}^2$; followed by an increase in dose by $0.5-1 \text{ J/cm}^2$ until the maximum radiation dose of 7.5 J/cm^2 is reached.

For laboratory assessment of the content of the studied cytokines - IL-1 β , IL-10, IL-17 and γ -INF in blood serum, the method of enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay was used.

Evaluation of the effectiveness of therapy was based on the criteria for the frequency of proven positive results in the conditions of usual use of UVA-1 methods and general photochemotherapy. At the same time, in accordance with the clinical guidelines of the European Academy of Dermatovenereology (2009), successful treatment was understood as complete or almost complete resolution of psoriatic efflorescences (PASI decrease by $\geq 90\%$) or cases in which treatment was completed with a PASI decrease by $\geq 75\%$.

The undertaken therapy was regarded as ineffective (unsuccessful) with the final values of the dynamics of the PASI < 75 index.

Results and its discussion. All patients participating in the study received traditional complex therapy for psoriasis: detoxification, hyposensitizing drugs, hepatoprotectors, antihistamines, topical emollients. The clinical efficacy of far

long-wave ultraviolet therapy (UVA-1) was assessed using an objective indicator of the prevalence and severity of the psoriatic process - the PASI index. The effect of this method of phototherapy on the quality of life of patients was assessed using the DLQI questionnaire on days 0 and 21 inpatient treatment. In patients suffering from moderate psoriasis, as a result of UVA-1 therapy, the level of PASI values varied in the range of 0-5, which indicates the resolution of the pathological process on the skin. The decrease in the PASI index in patients suffering from severe dermatosis did not reach the threshold of 5, corresponding to a significant improvement or improvement in the condition of the skin. In the group of patients who received general photochemotherapy with the internal use of a photosensitizer as part of complex treatment, this feature was not recorded.

Table №1. Dynamics of the PASI index in patients with psoriasis before and after therapy (units)

Type of therapy	Number of patients	Until treatment	After treatment
PUVA	30	29,70±1,35	4,29±0,22
UVA-1	40	28,89±0,92	4,55±0,19

The value of the DLQI index before the start of therapy in the main and control groups was 16.7±0.88 and 17.53±0.97, respectively. A significant decrease in the DLQI index values both in the main group receiving far long-wave ultraviolet therapy (UVA-1) (7.67±0.49;) and in the group using PUVA therapy (8.67±0.60)

Table 2. Values of the DLQI index in patients with psoriasis before and after therapy (units)

Type of therapy	Until treatment	After treatment
PUVA	17,53±0,97	8,67±0,60
UVA-1	16,7±0,88	7,67±0,49

When analyzing the results of laboratory studies, it was stated that the average value of the absolute concentrations of the studied parameters of the cytokine

profile (IL-1 β , IL-10, IL-17 and γ -INF) in the peripheral blood of patients with psoriasis was higher. In the general group of people suffering from psoriasis, the level of IL-10 significantly exceeded normal values and averaged 59.42 \pm 3.59 p μ g/ml; The highest absolute concentration of this cytokine was recorded in the group of patients with diffuse lesions of the skin. Also, in patients with a PASI index >35, the level of IL-10 significantly exceeded the average value of the general group of patients with psoriasis.

The concentration of IL-17, the average value of which was 21.44 \pm 1.33 p μ g/ml, IL-17, depending on the clinical form of the disease, was achieved in patients with exudative psoriasis 28.83 \pm 2.84 p μ g/ml, due to which it is interesting to note the possible relationship between the dynamics of IL-17 indicators and the exudative component of the inflammatory process.

In patients with psoriasis, the concentration of γ -INF was significantly higher (54.68 \pm 3.19 p μ g/ml; after therapy (12.39 \pm 0.25 p μ g/ml)

The effect of UVA-1 therapy was assessed by the dynamics of changes in the immunological parameters of the cytokine profile in patients with psoriasis, taking into account the immediate and long-term follow-up periods using the PASI and DLQI indices.

As a result of the treatment of patients with psoriasis in the therapeutic groups, the IL-10 index significantly decreased (in the UVA-1 group 3.57 \pm 0.25 p μ g / ml; p0.05), which indicates an equal effect of these methods of treatment on the level of IL-10 in serum of patients participating in the study. However, there was no statistically significant equality of IL-10 values in the patient groups and the control value in the donor group (p0.05), and it was statistically different from the values in the UVA-1 group.

Table 3. Parameters of the cytokine profile in patients with psoriasis before and after treatment.

Cytokine profile indicators	PUVA		UVA-1	
	Until treatment	After treatment	Until treatment	After treatment
IL-10	59,42 \pm 3,59p μ g/ml	3,57 \pm 0,25p μ g/ml	59,42 \pm 3,59p μ g/ml	3,27 \pm 0,25p μ g/ml
IL-17	28,83 \pm 2,84p μ g/ml,	2,33 \pm 0,17p μ g/ml	28,83 \pm 2,84p μ g/ml	2,33 \pm 0,17p μ g/ml

γ -INF	54,68±3,19pkg/ ml	12,39±0,25 pkg/ml	54,68±3,19pkg/ ml	12,39±0,25 pkg/ml
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As a result of UVA-1 therapy, out of 40 patients in the main group, a decrease in PASI by $\geq 90\%$ was noted in 16 (40%) people. Eleven patients (27.5%) had a decrease in PASI of $\geq 75\%$.

Conclusion: Thus, in accordance with the GCP standard, the effectiveness (frequency of proven positive effects) of UVA-1 therapy - 67.5%, PUVA therapy - 76.7%, respectively. Despite the fact that the effectiveness of UVA-1 therapy in the observed patients was lower compared to the group receiving photochemotherapy, this method does not have the limitations traditionally associated with the need to use photosensitizers in photochemotherapy. During therapy, patients treated with UVA-1 therapy tolerated the treatment satisfactorily. However, 7 (17.5%) patients noted the occurrence of minor dryness of the skin that did not affect the continuation of treatment, which could be corrected with external emollients and did not affect the course of therapy. The above adverse events did not reduce phototherapy compliance and did not require discontinuation. In 17 (42.5%) cases, the appearance of secondary hyperpigmentation of the skin in the areas of resolution of efflorescences was noted, which also did not affect the procedures. 2 (5%) patients noticed an increase in the ambient temperature inside the photocabin during the procedure, which, however, did not cause them to refuse to continue therapy. In 30 (100%) patients who received PUVA therapy, no hypersensitivity reactions to photosensitizing drugs were noted. 5 (16.6%) patients complained of nausea and vomiting during treatment. 21 (70%) of the observed persons in this therapeutic group were disturbed by burning sensations during and after the procedure. In 24 (80%) cases, secondary hyperpigmentation was noted at the site of efflorescences. 4 (13.3%) patients required an additional prescription of NSAIDs due to the presence of complaints of headache after taking a photosensitizing agent. 4 (13.3%) patients noted moderate pain in the epigastric region. Thus, the use of long-range long-wave ultraviolet UVA-1 therapy as part of the complex treatment of patients with psoriasis is an effective treatment method, and has a higher safety profile and good compliance compared to general photochemotherapy with the internal use of photosensitizers.

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